

Targeting neuroinflammation to combat pathological pain

Rita Silva, Joana Menezes, Silvia Fanton, Hans-Georg Schaible, Marzia Malcangio

Chronic pain: the 'invisible' disability

An increased or decreased ability to perceive pain has drastic and costly effects on the European population in terms of their performance at work and daily quality of life (European Pain Federation, 2016). Specifically, 19 per cent of adult Europeans experience moderate to severe chronic pain due to musculoskeletal conditions and neuropathic pain states. In 50 per cent of these cases, the treatment provided for their chronic pain is inadequate (Breivik *et al.*, 2006). Pain is also a major comorbidity in age-related neurodegenerative diseases (Wang *et al.*, 2018). With the EU population aged > 65 predicted to nearly double by 2060, reaching 151 million, pain management is a significant public health concern.

Current painkillers used for chronic pain conditions are only partially effective, leaving two-thirds of pain sufferers untreated (Hecke *et al.*, 2013). Antidepressants, anti-epileptic drugs and opioids are used for neuropathic pain relief with varying levels of success. NSAIDs are the main class of analgesics used in people with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) (Walsh and McWilliams, 2014). Paracetamol is used as analgesic medication to address pain in people with dementia (Achterberg *et al.*, 2019). However, over-the-counter analgesics are associated with severe side effects, limiting their application in neurodegeneration disease patients. Novel, more effective treatments for chronic pain are required.

Neuroinflammation

Neuroinflammation is the inflammatory response associated with damage in the central nervous system (CNS) and peripheral nervous system (PNS). It may contribute to various pain states, encompassing those with either a peripheral or CNS origin.

Peripheral nerve injuries and chronic inflammation in musculoskeletal diseases may result in pain that persists after the resolution of damage and the active inflammatory phase in the joint. This indicates that independent pain mechanisms may develop during the course of these diseases, resulting in chronic pain conditions. Such pathological pain is a maladaptive

mechanism that remains difficult to treat with current medicines in conditions like RA or peripheral (poly)neuropathies, i.e. Fabry disease (FD). The experience of pathological pain after CNS damage, such as in neurodegenerative diseases, is less predictable and more variable—exacerbating the difficulty in developing effective strategies to treat chronic pain (Lawn *et al.*, 2021).

Pain research initially focused on the role of neurons in pain mechanisms. The focus has now shifted onto the role of non-neuronal cells, including their communication with neurons through the cyto(chemo)kines that occurs due to their response to altered neuronal activity (Malcangio *et al.*, 2019). A stimulating proposal is that chronic pain could result from a dysregulation of non-neuronal glial function in the PNS and CNS (Ji *et al.*, 2016).

Acute pain results from the detection of dangerous stimuli by neurons in the periphery, which then transfer signals to the spinal cord and thence higher centres in the brain, where pain is recognised. We know that peripheral nerve and tissue damage result in neuronal sensitisation and inflammatory reactions locally, e.g. via macrophage accumulation and cyto(chemo)kine production. But this peripheral damage also results in increased neuronal firing in the spinal cord and brain (central sensitisation) remotely from the injury. Excessive

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the mechanisms and interactions in chronic pain in neuropathies and neurodegenerative and musculoskeletal diseases that are being investigated by the TOBeATPAIN consortium. Created with BioRender.com

neuronal firing in the spinal cord and brain causes significant activation of non-neuronal cells, namely microglia and astrocytes, leading to neuroinflammation (Xanthos and Sandkuhler, 2016; Ji *et al.*, 2018). In neurodegenerative diseases, direct damage of neurons in the brain is also associated with significant inflammation. This is, intriguingly, generated by a disruption—rather than augmentation—of neuron-non-neuronal cell signalling (Ransohoff, 2016). Under normal conditions, microglia and astrocytes communication

with neurons serves to maintain homeostasis. Neuroinflammation in neurodegenerative conditions defines the altered response of microglia and astrocytes to a signal change from injured neurons.

Therefore, it appears that pathological pain associated with inflammation after CNS or PNS damage may involve discrete mechanisms that result in neuron-non-neuronal cell signalling changes. These are being investigated by the TOBeATPAIN network (Figure 1).

The TOBeATPAIN project

TOBeATPAIN examines the neuroinflammation associated with pain in peripheral and central diseases to identify the critical non-neuronal cellular players and mediators involved in pathological pain signalling. The project aims to provide multidisciplinary training to 11 early stage researchers (ESRs) on investigating neuroinflammation-mediated mechanisms of pathological pain in neurodegenerative diseases, musculoskeletal conditions and peripheral neuropathies, and to train them to delineate novel therapeutic strategies (Figure 2).

TOBeATPAIN is testing two hypotheses. Firstly, neuroinflammation represents an underlying mechanism of pathological pain that occurs due to diseases within the brain and the PNS. Secondly, the precise mechanisms of neuroinflammation in peripheral and brain diseases share some features but also vary and possess individual characteristics.

TOBeATPAIN is structured around two scientific themes and has formulated three research objectives (Figure 3).

Neuroimmune interactions and pain in neurodegenerative conditions

Nearly 40–60 per cent of patients with neurodegenerative diseases are affected by the alteration of pain sensation (Borsook, 2012). Alzheimer's disease (AD) patients have a compromised ability to report pain, and untreated pain contributes to psychiatric symptoms of dementia (Corbett *et al.*, 2013; Husebo *et al.*, 2016). Notably, peripheral inflammation in musculoskeletal diseases is associated with increased risk for AD pathology, and high serum levels of proinflammatory cytokines in AD patients are associated with dementia (Holmes *et al.*, 2009). Importantly, AD is

Figure 2: Schematic overview over the fundamental research questions and possible answers of the TOBeATPAIN project.

Figure 3: Structure of the TOBeATPAIN project. Created with BioRender.com

considered a risk factor for the under-treatment of pain (Monroe *et al.*, 2016).

Pain is also a major non-motor symptom of Parkinson's Disease (PD), and between 40–80 per cent of people with PD suffer from chronic pain (Schapira *et al.*, 2017). The annual incidence of PD in Europe is 1 in 1,000 people. The first internationally validated pain rating scale for PD, as well as a patient completed pain questionnaire, has been generated in recognition of the high prevalence of pain in these patients, and the need for more effective treatments and a proper scale against

which to assess their efficacy (King's Parkinson's Disease Pain Scale) (Chaudhuri *et al.*, 2015). Neuronal degeneration affects neuronal function and provokes an intense reaction by microglia and astrocytes (neuroinflammation), which may give rise to pain depending on their phenotypes of activation. Recent genetic evidence suggests that microglia dysfunction makes a primary contribution to neurodegeneration, which opens new avenues for therapeutic target identification and exploitation (Ransohoff *et al.*, 2016).

TOBeATPAIN suggests that (micro) glial activation in areas of the brain and spinal cord devoted to pain signalling and perception may contribute to pathological pain specific to certain neurodegenerative diseases by releasing mediators such as the cyto(chemo)kines, which increase neuronal excitation. Thus, TASTPM mice (transgenic model of AD) display altered sensitivity to acute noxious thermal stimuli, cognition deficits, brain plaque pathology, spinal cord neuron β -amyloid expression, elevated microglial reactivity in the thalamus and increased opioidergic tone (Aman *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, in the 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA) nigrostriatal lesioned rat model of PD, they display mechanical allodynia (Domenici *et al.*, 2019).

To identify innovative targets for better pain control in neurodegenerative diseases, we aim to define the circumstances under which microglia and astrocyte activation produce pain, the mechanisms by which these non-neuronal cells contribute to altered pain sensitivity in AD and PD patients, in animal models of AD and PD as well as in *in vivo* models for measuring neuronal activity.

Neuroimmune interactions and pain in rheumatic diseases

RA is a debilitating and painful autoimmune disease affecting almost 1 per cent of the worldwide population, and fibromyalgia (FM)—which is a widespread pain syndrome—affects ~ 2 per cent of the population. Recent therapeutic progress in controlling this type of RA pain, generated in the periphery, includes anti-cytokine therapy (anti-TNF) (Monaco *et al.*, 2015). Nevertheless, pain is still a major issue reported by RA patients, and no specific analgesics for FM are provided to patients.

To identify novel targets that drive inflammatory pain in RA, preclinical

research will be conducted using animal models of RA. Relevantly, even though injection of collagen-type II antibodies induces a transient joint inflammation lasting 2–3 weeks, the animals develop a pain-like behaviour that persists beyond resolution of joint inflammation. The long-term changes in nociception are accompanied by up-regulation of factors in the dorsal root ganglia (DRG) and spinal cord, indicating that a transient antibody-driven joint inflammation may recruit pathways that drive a pain state characterised by a unique neurochemical profile (Su *et al.*, 2015).

Although spinal cord microglia and astrocytes play key roles alongside neurons in spinal pain transmission, TOBeATPAIN also aims to explore the role in pain processing played by glial cells located in the brain. The following two observations indicate that peripheral inflammation and pain in rheumatic conditions are associated with ongoing CNS neuroinflammation: (i) glia are activated in the brain of chronic low back pain patients (Loggia *et al.*, 2014); and (ii) levels of cytokines IL-1 β and IL-8 are elevated in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from RA and FM patients, respectively (Lampa *et al.*, 2012; Kosek *et al.*, 2015). Glial activation plays critical roles in inflammatory and neuropathic pain—as reported in several imaging studies which have used ligands that bind to the translocator protein (TSPO). An increased TSPO activation has been linked with the release of cytokines such as IL-1 β and IL-8 (Kosek *et al.*, 2016).

We aim to define the mechanisms by which macrophage activity in DRG and microglia and astrocyte activity in the brain and spinal cord contributes to pain in FM patients and animal models of RA and FM.

Neuroimmune interactions and pain in peripheral neuropathies

Chronic pain syndromes, which develop after peripheral nerve damage, trauma and inflammation, are characterised by severe pain. Current therapies, although reasonably effective in some subgroups of patients, are not devoid of side effects. Plastic neuronal changes in peripheral nerves and spinal cord underlie chronic neuropathic pain resulting from pronociceptive systems dominance over the effect of endogenous anti-nociceptive systems. Nevertheless, anti-nociceptive systems, such as the endocannabinoid system, play inhibitory roles in controlling neuropathic pain. Cannabinoids receptors, namely CB₁ and CB₂ receptors, offer therapeutic targets for the control of neuropathic pain (Maldonado *et al.*, 2016). Besides neurons, immune cells in the periphery (at the site of nerve damage) and in the spinal cord (remotely located from damage) play facilitative roles in both induction and maintenance of chronic pain.

TOBeATPAIN will establish whether the phenotype of microglial activation in the spinal cord after peripheral nerve injury differs from peripheral inflammatory conditions. This project also predicts that the modalities of glial activation differ in pain states and different diseases.

We aim to define the mechanisms by which microglia and astrocyte activity in the CNS and immune cells in the periphery contribute to pain associated with peripheral neuropathies in patients and in a mouse model of FD. FD is an X-linked lysosomal storage disease with loss of function mutations of the gene (GLA), causing an accumulation of glycosphingolipids and an early life neuropathic pain phenotype. We also explore the potential anti-nociceptive effect of medical marijuana extract via activation of CB₂ receptors expressed by immune cells (Komorowska-Müller *et al.*,

2020). Indeed, CB₂ agonists reduce the release of pro-nociceptive factors from microglia (Puffenberger *et al.*, 2000), and overexpression of CB₂ receptors is associated with reduced neuropathic pain behaviour (Racz, 2008).

In neuropathic pain conditions, there is a significant elevation of proinflammatory cytokines in the blood of patients with painful (but not painless) peripheral neuropathy (Sommer *et al.*, 2016) and the significant deficits in neuronal function in a mouse model of FD predict that alterations in nociceptive processing in the CNS are related to neuroimmune deficits. Although immune reactivity has been described in FD patients (Mauhin, 2015), the role of the immune system and neuroimmune interactions in FD neuropathic pain have yet to be investigated.

TOBeATPAIN proposes an innovative approach to control neuropathic pain by targeting CB₂: building on solid data generated with genetically modified mice, there is strong evidence for a beneficial effect of CB₂ receptor agonists in the regulation of central immune cell reactivity, which can result in the reduction of neuropathic pain (Racz, 2008).

With a clear therapeutic angle, TOBeATPAIN aims to define the mechanisms by which microglia and astrocyte activity in the CNS and macrophages and T cells in the periphery contribute to pain in models of FD and peripheral nerve trauma as well as in neuropathic patients. We will also exploit the potential anti-nociceptive effect of medical marijuana extracts—devoid of classical cannabidiol or tetrahydrocannabinol (THC)—via CB₂ receptor activation expressed by immune cells.

TOBeATPAIN project in a nutshell

Question

Do mechanisms of neuroinflammation offer innovative targets for pathological pain therapy? This is the central question of the programme. Several further questions stem from this. Are there common mechanisms at work during neurodegenerative diseases and chronic pain? Do changes in the CNS pain areas triggered by inflammatory processes in arthritis facilitate the generation of pathological pain in neurodegenerative diseases? How do (micro)glial activation states in neurodegeneration compare to glial reactive reaction in chronic pain states? Is there a difference due to the fact that in neurodegeneration the brain is the main site of neuroinflammation whilst in chronic pain the PNS and spinal cord are the major sites?

Answer

TOBeATPAIN addresses the need of EU society for novel pain treatments by taking an innovative strategy and a multidisciplinary, translational approach. TOBeATPAIN proposes to focus on non-neuronal cells rather than neurons. Specifically, we will **compare** and **contrast** the mechanisms by which central immune cells (microglia) and astrocytes, and peripheral macrophages and T cells impact on neuronal activity in neurodegenerative and chronic pain syndromes. We predict that identification and description of the mechanisms underlying neuroinflammation offer the innovative answer that typifies the cutting edge approach of TOBeATPAIN.

[Click here to view references](#)

PROJECT SUMMARY

TOBeATPAIN takes an innovative approach to investigate neuroinflammation associated with pain in peripheral and central diseases and pinpoint critical non-neuronal cellular players and mediators involved in pathological pain signalling. This project is structured around three research objectives to uncover the mechanisms by which (micro)glial cells affect pain in neurodegenerative conditions, fibromyalgia, rheumatoid arthritis, and peripheral neuropathies.

PROJECT LEAD

Marzia Malcangio is Professor of Neuropharmacology and Head of Wolfson CARD at King's College London. The W-CARD department seeks to increase our understanding and develop new treatments to restore normal sensory function and aid injury recovery. Her research group is focused on delineating neuroimmune interactions in chronic pain settings and identify new analgesic targets. She has published over 120 papers on pain and coordinates the TOBeATPAIN network.

PROJECT PARTNERS

TOBeATPAIN offers an unique training platform with the active involvement of five universities (King's College London (KCL), Karolinska Institutet (KI), Medizinischen Universität Innsbruck (MUI), Universitätsklinikum Jena (UKJ) and Universitätsklinikum Würzburg (UKW) and three biotech SMEs (Kancera AB, Mabtech AB and EURICE), 2 large companies (Eli Lilly and Company Ltd and Bionorica Research GmbH) and 1 non-profit research charity (Alzheimer's Society UK).

CONTACT DETAILS

Professor Marzia Malcangio,
Professor of Neuropharmacology

Wolfson Centre for Age Related Diseases
Institute of Psychiatry, Psychology &
Neuroscience, Wolfson Wing, Hodgkin Building,
Guy's Campus, London SE1 1UL

 +44 (0)20 7848 6092

 marzia.malcangio@kcl.ac.uk

 www.tobeatpain-itn.net

 @AtpainBe

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